

REQUIREMENTS FOR YOUNG LEADERS IN CULTURE AND
ARTS MANAGEMENT

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Annotation: The article describes the qualities that determine the potential of students and their potential during their work. Also, the causes of some disagreements and problems in the relationship between the manager and the employee and their solutions are given.

Key words: competence, employee, leader, image, potential, leadership, speaker, decision, task, addressee

**Birovning fazilatiga baho berish uchun, albatta, shu
fazilatning juda bo'lmaganda bir
miqdoriga ega bo'lish kerak.**

V.Shekspir

Today, there is a comprehensive system for improving the political culture of our people, increasing the role of national spiritual values in the education of young people, and widely promoting our customs and traditions. Also, the activities of cultural and art institutions under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, including theaters, circuses, art palaces, libraries, recreation parks and cultural centers, the reforms carried out in them, management policies, the position of leading personnel among employees and it is very important that they can fully respond to the demands placed on them. By the way, as the Honorable President said, "We should never forget one fact, if culture and art do not develop in our country, society will not develop" [1:23]. Currently, there are more than 200 departments of culture and tourism, 832 cultural centers and 597 artistic amateur teams that received the title of "People's Amateur Team" and "Children's Model Team", 39 state theaters, 57 cultural and recreational parks, the level of work efficiency in 323 children's music and art schools, meaningful organization of youth free time, the scope of spiritual and educational promotion activities among our people, extra-budgetary Achieving high ranks in statistical indicators, such as indicators of earning additional funds, whether employees are specialists or non-specialists, and the position among all cultural and art organizations in the republic,

without a doubt, depends on the performance of the head of the organization or institution and the potential abilities of the employees. is a directly relevant issue. Therefore, we want to focus on the qualities and requirements of young leaders in the management of culture and art.

Indeed, when we look at history, we can be sure that the history of mankind is full of various forms of management (leadership) and their complexity as our way of life changes and sharpens over the course of centuries. Staying behind the rapidly developing times has a significant impact not only on young leaders, but also on the creation of a modern personality in each person. For example, culture and art institutions, in particular, cultural centers, "have reached the same age", "think that I should retire", "inactive from social networks", "do not want to accept and implement the new It is no exaggeration to say that the leaders still occupy the "chair of leadership" is one of the most painful points of our industry. As Tolstoy said, "Acting because everyone thinks like this" leads to the worst tragedies" [2:27]. True, they may not have the experience gained over the years in young management personnel, but incompetence and lack of enthusiasm open the first doors for ineffective results of every work.

Today, not only in the field of culture and art, but also in the process of management on every front, we hear disagreements between the leader and the employee, such as "don't rush, I will pour water under you." I think that such irreconcilable relations in many cases are the reason for the incompetence of leaders during their work and, most importantly, their inability to fully meet the requirements set for leaders. In fact, the impression a leader makes on the imagination of his subordinates on the first day of work is reflected in the relationship with the leader during his career. Leadership potential plays a key role in organizing effective management of young leaders. As a result of observations, the following set of requirements are set for young leaders in this field, which is called "art management" in many developed countries:notiqlik;

- listening culture;
- leadership;
- time planning and saving;
- making the right decision;
- control;
- political knowledge;
- legal literacy;
- ability to use modern technologies;
- economic knowledge;
- respect for national values.

In fact, as President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "Today, life itself requires proper organization of our work, ensuring its effectiveness, raising the quality of the entire management system to the level of modern requirements. However, no matter what obstacles and difficulties, acute and urgent problems we face on our way, we have the right to make hasty, rash decisions, to allow ill-considered actions. "q" [3:3]. Of course, in addition to fulfilling the duties assigned to young leaders within the law, it is necessary to be a mature and perfect person in terms of humanity. As we dwell on the above-mentioned characteristics of the leader's potential, it is important to emphasize the quality of leadership among them. Leadership means the ability to influence, persuade and motivate people to achieve results. Only when the leader is a good speaker, the leader is recognized as a master of his work. If he is able to convey his thoughts sufficiently, if he is eloquent, the sphere of influence on people will be so wide. A beautiful speech is the basis of the appearance of a modern leader and the phenomenon of image. As Napoleon said, "Those who cannot hold their speech cannot be leaders." A leader is a good speaker it is desirable to have the ability to listen to the addressee (the person to whom the speech is addressed) as well.

It should be noted that it is not without benefits for a modern leader to have sufficient knowledge of image creation. After all, the famous American general Elbion Hay said, "A man's image always speaks about him behind his back" [4:10]. Yes, indeed, image is an English word that means "appearance", "appearance", and people around judge not only leaders, but every person based on their image. To put it metaphorically, a person's identity and image are like his face and image. If the beauty of Sirat is not shown in the picture, no one can enjoy it. Therefore, first of all, it is important to achieve the beauty of syrat, that is, to have a good character and bring this quality to the picture. As Jalaluddin Rumi, one of the great figures of world literature, said, look like you are or be like what you seem. The political knowledge, legal literacy, ability to use modern technologies, economic knowledge, respect for national values and self-confidence of modern leaders serve as the main weapon for having a unique image and do not leave others indifferent. Today, due to insufficient political and economic knowledge and low legal literacy of young leaders, it has a negative impact on the overall development of cultural and art institutions. It is considered one of the urgent problems - the lack of economic potential of the leaders is the main factor in the financial weakness and inability of cultural and art organizations to provide for themselves. In my opinion, the inactivity of leaders in political processes and their lack of reaction to situations directly related to their work is the main reason for the deterioration of the image of the leader and the decrease in the authority of the organization, as well as the loss of the position

of the leader among the employees. In particular, the Department of Culture and Art Management of the State Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan and the network center for retraining and professional development of Pedagogical personnel under the institute, with the senior teacher Mominmirzo Kholmo'minov, present culture and art I talked about the knowledge and management potential of the leading personnel operating in the field and got the necessary conclusions. "From April to October 2022, I will teach the leaders and chief experts of cultural centers who came to improve their qualifications at the Pedagogical Personnel Retraining and Professional Development Network Center of the State Institute of Arts and Culture of Uzbekistan. All the leaders are old and experienced, but they do not have enough political and economic knowledge, they do not want to be active in political processes. One day I asked about the website "regulation.uz". There was no sound from any of them. This is the work of leaders who are indifferent to their work," said M. Kholmo'minov. Therefore, it is the demand of today's time for young personnel to work on themselves and to be perfect owners of 31 competencies defined by world standards. Of course, this is the same knowledge criterion that is required in all fields and specialties. In short, the individual and collective potential of the leader (director, head) is the most important factor in the process of both creative and administrative management in the field of culture and art, which is one of the leading areas in the development of New Uzbekistan. That is, every action of the leader can have not only a positive, but also a negative effect on the reputation of the enterprise or organization. Since the field of culture and art is considered an activity directly related to people, a leader who has the ability to organize effective management in all aspects, in modern language, is considered an "intelligent leader".

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VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5

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VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5

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VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5

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VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5

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VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5

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VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5

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VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5

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